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Effect Of Health Education On Knowledge Of Occupational Hazard And Safety Measures Among Palm Oil Workers In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of health education on the knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures among of palm oil workers in Delta State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design with 150 participants selected through multi-stage sampling was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire (KOHQS) with a reliability index of 0.70. The questionnaire was administered before and after a structured health education intervention, achieving a 95.3% success rate. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v.25, involved percentage, t-test, and ANCOVA. Findings revealed significant post-intervention improvements in workers' KAP. Mean knowledge scores increased from 66.0% (pretest) to 85.1% (posttest), reflecting a gain of 19.1%. There was no significant difference in the effect of health education on knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures based on gender, age, and work experience ($P>0.05$). The study concluded that health education significantly enhanced occupational health and safety outcomes such as knowledge. It was recommended among others that agricultural business employers and industry leaders should institutionalize workplace safety training programs as regular activities in the palm oil industry.

Keywords: Health Education, Knowledge, Occupational Hazards, Safety Measures, Palm Oil Workers

INTRODUCTION

Palm oil production is an agricultural pursuit that may be challenging and at the same time highly rewarding, as it possesses favourable technical qualities and an economic benefit, being one of the most produced and consumed oils worldwide (Virgin et al., 2022). According to Gunn (2014), it is recognized for its appeal to users, its price advantage, and technical superiority among numerous edible oils, due to its availability throughout the year.

Various injuries may occur among oil palm workers, including those who are experienced and familiar with equipment and working environments. Hazardous agricultural substances, such as pesticides, fertilizers, flammable liquids, and other solvents, can cause acute or chronic injuries or illnesses among palm oil workers. Although the use of modern equipment has led to a significant increase in production, mechanization has also contributed to the occurrence of hazards, injuries, and illnesses within the palm oil industry (Decker, 2021). This situation led the researcher to develop an interest in examining the hazards associated with palm oil work. According to Dennis and Romanus (2018), the palm oil processing industry in Delta State, Nigeria, plays a significant role in the country's agricultural sector. However,

workers in this industry are exposed to considerable occupational hazards and accidents, resulting in health issues and work-related injuries. These hazards arise from physical, chemical, biological, ergonomic, and psychosocial sources.

Living in a community where palm oil processing constitutes a major agricultural activity and a substantial means of livelihood, the researcher observed that many workers show little concern for the dangers associated with palm oil processing. Palm oil production remains a common occupation among rural dwellers who often utilise old, crude methods for cultivation, harvesting, and processing. As a result, they are highly exposed to various forms of physical, chemical, mechanical, and psychosocial hazards inherent in their processes.

Several occupational hazards are common in palm oil processing, such as mechanical hazards from machinery and equipment, slippery surfaces, inadequate lighting, and improper housekeeping practices. The International Labour Organisation [ILO] (2018) and Tarurhor and Emudainohwo (2020) noted that potential hazards in palm oil processing include exposure to toxic substances, hazardous chemicals during refining, insect bites, and exposure to disease vectors like mosquitoes during farm clearing and maintenance, including harvesting by traditional climbing methods.

To reduce or prevent these dangers, many health promotion practices involving hazard control measures have been recommended by notable health and safety organizations. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO) (2018), typical control measures include installing safety guards on machinery, conducting regular maintenance and inspections, designing facilities to reduce ergonomic risks, developing and enforcing standard operating procedures, providing comprehensive training and education on hazard awareness, proper equipment handling, and emergency response procedures, implementing regular safety audits and risk assessments, and supplying appropriate Personal Protective Equipment (PPE).

Health and safety education plays a crucial role in enhancing knowledge, awareness, and behaviour relating to health and safety practices. Research has shown that health education interventions significantly increase workers' understanding of workplace hazards and their capacity to identify and apply proper safety measures (Che Huei et al., 2020; Biswas et al., 2021; Hasan & Kamardeen, 2022). Health education also helps foster a culture of safety and encourages positive safety conduct among workers (Achalu, 2020). By increasing awareness of the importance of safety procedures and offering practical guidance, health education programmes can influence workers to cultivate safe working habits, actively participate in identifying and reporting hazards, and take responsibility for their own and their colleagues' well-being.

Health education equips workers with the necessary information to recognise and manage workplace hazards effectively. Such education consists of programmes designed to improve workers' awareness of potential risks and to teach the utilisation of control measures to prevent accidents and injuries (Kyalu, 2020). The study by Azizah et al. (2019) in the manufacturing industry demonstrated the impact of health education interventions in enhancing workers' understanding of workplace dangers. Workers who received focused health education showed greater ability to recognise potential dangers and apply safety measures, thus reducing workplace injuries and promoting a safer environment (Guzman et al., 2022).

Delta State, Nigeria, created in 1991 and consisting of 25 Local Government Areas, is endowed with various solid mineral resources, such as oil, industrial clay, silica, lignite, kaolin, tar sand, decorative rocks, and limestone (My Guide Nigeria, 2019). Delta State also thrives in agricultural produce and remains a major contributor to palm tree and crop production in Nigeria. By imparting knowledge specific to the occupational hazards of palm oil processing and related control measures, health and safety education prepares workers to properly recognise, assess, and manage workplace hazards.

Human health behaviour is influenced by several demographic factors, including age, gender, and work experience (ILO, 2020; WHO, 2020). In occupational safety, these factors are significant as they affect individuals' perceptions and responses to safety measures. Age, defined as the number of years an individual has lived from birth (Luo et al., 2022), influences physical ability and risk perception. Younger workers may exhibit overconfidence and take more risks, whereas older workers might have reduced

physical strength and slower reaction times. Therefore, training must be tailored to accommodate these differences, maintaining high safety standards for all ages (Odion-Obomhense & Ejikeme, 2022).

Gender, understood here from a biological perspective as male or female status (White et al., 2021), plays a part in health due to physiological and psychological differences. Studies indicate that women may be more prone to ergonomic issues because of body structure and traditional job roles (Biswas et al., 2021; Pamidimukkala & Kermanshachi, 2022; Santoro et al., 2022), whereas men may be more exposed to heavy physical tasks (Santoro et al., 2022). Ensuring that safety equipment and training suit both genders is necessary to reduce risk (Dollard & Nesar, 2023). Furthermore, work experience affects safety practices. Experienced workers generally recognise hazards better but may also become complacent, necessitating ongoing training (Che Huei et al., 2020; Crawford et al., 2020; Amponsah-Tawiah & Mensah, 2021).

In rural Nigeria, addressing these demographic differences among palm oil workers is critical due to the hazardous and labour-intensive nature of the industry. Implementing effective safety protocols and continuous demographic-tailored training could significantly enhance safety outcomes. However, achieving this requires understanding how these factors influence safety practices among palm oil workers.

Theoretical frameworks such as Safety Culture Theory and the Health Belief Model offer ways to understand and improve health behaviour among palm oil workers. Safety Culture Theory stresses the importance of shared safety values and proactive safety management (Asamani, 2020). The Health Belief Model explains health behaviours by considering perceived risks, benefits, barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy (Green et al., 2020). Applying these frameworks through health education among palm oil workers in Delta State may greatly improve safety practices and reduce occupational hazards and accidents.

Despite the known hazards, limited literature exists that specifically addresses occupational risks and safety practices among palm oil workers in Delta State. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of health education intervention on knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding occupational hazards and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State by answering the following research questions:

3. What is the effect of health education on level of knowledge of occupational hazard and safety measure among palm oil workers in Delta State?
4. What is the effect of health education on level of knowledge of occupational hazard and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience)?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

4. Health education has no significant effect on level of knowledge of occupational hazard and safety measure among palm oil workers in Delta State.
5. Health education has no significant effect on level of knowledge of occupational hazard and safety practices among palm oil processing worker in Delta State based on selected demographic variables (gender, age and work experience).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a pretest-posttest quasi experimental research design. The population for the study was one thousand, five hundred and twenty two (1522) local oil millers in Delta state. This population was the number of local oil millers across the 25 Local Government Areas in Delta state (Delta State Oil Millers Association [DSOMA], 2024). 150 participants selected through multi-stage sampling was employed. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire titled "Knowledge, of Occupational Hazard and Safety Questionnaire (KOHSQ), with a reliability index of 0.70. The instrument was sectioned into two. Section A, consisted of 3 items dedicated to demographic characteristics of the respondents, while section B consisted of items that were used to gather the respondent's knowledge of occupational hazards and safety. The questionnaire was administered before a structured health education intervention. The study intervention was designed as a six-week health education program aimed at

improving the knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State. After the structured health education intervention, the questionnaire was re-administered achieving a 95.3% success rate. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v.25, involved percentage, t-test, and ANCOVA.

RESULTS

Demographic Data

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Factor	Groups	F	%
Gender	Female	87	60.8
	Male	56	39.2
	Total	143	100.0
Age	≤20 years	9	6.3
	21-30 years	49	34.3
	31-40 years	43	30.1
	≥41 years	42	29.4
	Total	143	100.0
Work Experience	<1 year	8	5.6
	1-5 years	22	15.4
	6-10 years	31	21.7
	≥11 years	82	57.3
	Total	143	100.0

Table 1 above revealed that 87 study participants (60.8%) were females while 39.2% were males. This implied that more females engaged in palm oil processing business than males. The age distribution of the palm oil workers showed that majority of the participants (34.3%) are between 21–30 years, followed by those aged 31–40 years (30.1%) and ≥41 years (29.4%). Only 6.3% are 20 years or younger, indicating that most workers are adults in their productive age range. Also, the data revealed that majority of the participant, 57.3%, have over 11 years of experience. Those with 6–10 years of experience make up 21.7%, followed by 15.4% with 1–5 years, and only 5.6% have less than one year. This suggests a workforce with large industry experience.

Table 2: Percentage analysis on effect of health education on level of knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures among palm oil workers in Delta State

S/N	Statements	<u>Pretest (N=143)</u>				<u>Posttest (N=143)</u>			
		Correct		Incorrect		Correct		Incorrect	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
4	There is the problem of high temperature in palm oil processing. (T)	80	56	62	44	127	89	15	11
5	Dehydration as a result of high temperature occurs in palm oil processing. (T)	111	78	31	22	120	84	22	16
6	Heat exhaustion results from prolonged exposure to heat. (T)	85	60	57	40	110	77	32	23
7	Palm oil processors often experience back pains. (T)	111	78	31	22	128	90	14	10
8	Palm oil processors often experience joint problems. (T)	80	56	62	44	135	95	7	5
9	Palm oil processors often experience	97	68	45	32	131	92	11	8

	muscle soreness. (T)								
10	Palm oil processors are often victims of cuts, burns, falling objects, and injuries from machines. (T)	85	60	57	40	114	80	28	20
11	Palm oil processors are often victims of cuts and puncture injuries from sharp objects and burns. (T)	104	73	38	27	128	90	14	10
12	Palm oil processors are often victims of falling and trips from height and slippery floors. (T)	75	53	67	47	110	77	32	23
13	Palm oil processors are often victims of burns from hot substances such as hot water, hot charcoal, and hot oil, including hot drums. (T)	104	73	38	27	102	72	40	28
14	Exposure to pesticides often affects palm oil workers negatively. (T)	101	71	41	29	128	90	14	10
15	Exposure to herbicides has a negative effect on palm oil workers. (T)	80	56	62	44	127	89	15	11
16	Constant use of cleaning agents such as detergents causes skin irritation for workers. (T)	111	78	31	22	120	84	22	16
17	Malaria, Dengue fever often attack palm oil processors. (T)	85	60	57	40	110	77	32	23
18	Poor working conditions affect palm oil workers psychologically. (T)	111	78	31	22	128	90	14	10
19	Low wages affect palm oil workers psychologically. (T)	80	56	62	44	135	95	7	5
20	Noise pollution is a significant hazard in palm oil mills. (T)	97	68	45	32	131	92	11	8
21	There are dangerous reptiles in palm oil plantations. (T)	85	60	57	40	114	80	28	20
22	There are dangerous insects in palm oil plantations. (T)	104	73	38	27	128	90	14	10
23	Palm oil workers experience exacerbation as a result of exposure to palm oil fumes. (T)	75	53	67	47	110	77	32	23
24	Palm oil workers experience respiratory irritation as a result of exposure to palm oil fumes. (T)	104	73	38	27	102	72	40	28
25	Palm oil workers experience breathing difficulties due to exposure to palm oil fumes. (T)	101	71	41	29	128	90	14	10
26	Wearing protective gloves is necessary when handling chemicals during the palm oil processing. (T)	80	56	62	44	127	89	15	11
27	It is safe to operate machinery without following the lockout/tagout procedures in the palm oil mill. (F)	111	78	31	22	120	84	22	16
28	Regular cleaning and maintenance of equipment reduces the risk of accidents in the palm oil mill. (T)	85	60	57	40	110	77	32	23

29	Workers do not need to wear masks when exposed to dust and fumes in the palm oil production area. (F)	111	78	31	22	128	90	14	10
30	Proper lifting techniques are used to prevent back injuries when handling heavy palm oil products. (T)	80	56	62	44	135	95	7	5
31	Consuming food or drinks in the processing area is safe and does not pose any contamination risks. (F)	97	68	45	32	131	92	11	8
32	It is important to know the location of emergency exits and fire extinguishers in the palm oil mill. (T)	85	60	57	40	114	80	28	20
33	Safety training is only required for new employees and does not need to be refreshed regularly. (F)	104	73	38	27	128	90	14	10
34	Regular inspection of palm tree climbing ropes before use reduces the risk of fall accidents among harvesters. (T)	75	53	67	47	110	77	32	23
35	Proper placement of sharp objects immediately after use reduces the incidence of cut and puncture accidents. (T)	104	73	38	27	102	72	40	28
36	Wearing safety gadgets does not prevent accidents in the palm oil workplace. (F)	101	71	41	29	128	90	14	10
Aggregate % Gain		94	66.0	48	34.0	121	85.1	21	14.9

The data in table 2 showed that the mean data indicates that the health education intervention resulted in a significant knowledge improvement among palm oil workers regarding hazards and safety measures. The mean percentage of correct responses increased from 66.0% in the pretest to 85.1% in the posttest, representing a mean gain of 19.1%. This suggests that the intervention effectively enhanced workers' awareness of safety protocols.

Table 3: Summary of Z-test analysis of the effect of health education on level of knowledge of occupational hazard and safety measure among palm oil workers in Delta State

Variables	N	\bar{x}	St.D	Mean Diff	z-Stats	Eta ²	P.value
Pretest Aggregate Attitude	143	1.11	0.945				
Posttest Aggregate Attitude	143	1.56	0.638	0.45	4.724	0.261	0.002

P<0.05

Table 3 presents a Z-test analysis assessing the impact of health education on palm oil workers' knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures in Delta State. The mean knowledge score increased from 1.11 (pretest) to 1.56 (posttest), with a mean difference of 0.45. The calculated Z-statistic (4.724) indicates a significant improvement. The effect size (Eta² = 0.261) suggests a moderate effect of health education. The p-value (0.002) is statistically significant (P < 0.05), confirming that the observed change is unlikely due to chance. This implies that health education effectively enhanced workers' knowledge of occupational safety.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA to establish the effect of Health education on level of knowledge of occupational hazard among palm oil processing worker in Delta state based on gender, age and work experience.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects								
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P.value	Partial Squared	Eta	
Corrected Model	1.169 ^a	23	.051	.832	.685	.139		
Intercept	18.356	1	18.356	300.678	.000	.716		
Gender	.002	1	.002	.032	.858	.000		
Age	.127	3	.042	.694	.558	.017		
Work_experience	.084	3	.028	.460	.711	.011		
Gender * Age	.016	3	.005	.086	.968	.002		
Gender * Work_experience	.084	3	.028	.457	.713	.011		
Age * Work_experience	.220	6	d.037	.601	.729	.029		
Gender * Age * Work_experience	.063	3	.021	.344	.794	.009		
Error	7.265	119	.061					
Total	134.000	143						
Corrected Total	8.434	142						

The ANCOVA results in Table 4 examined whether demographic variables (gender, age, and work experience) and their interactions significantly affect the effect of health education on knowledge of occupational hazards among palm oil processing workers. Gender did not have a significant effect ($F = 0.032$, $p = 0.858$, $\text{Eta}^2 = 0.000$), indicating no difference in the effectiveness of health education between male and female workers. Similarly, age ($F = 0.694$, $p = 0.558$, $\text{Eta}^2 = 0.017$) and work experience ($F = 0.460$, $p = 0.711$, $\text{Eta}^2 = 0.011$) had no significant effects, suggesting that workers of different age groups and levels of experience benefited equally. Furthermore, the interactive effects among gender, age, and work experience were all non-significant ($p > 0.05$, $p > 0.05$), indicating no combined influence on post-knowledge. These findings demonstrate that health education had a uniform impact across demographic categories and experience levels.

DISCUSSION

The current study demonstrated that health education interventions significantly improved palm oil processing workers' knowledge of occupational hazards and safety measures in Delta State, Nigeria. Pre-intervention assessments revealed moderate levels of knowledge, which notably increased post-intervention. Workers became better equipped to identify hazards such as exposure to dangerous machinery, toxic chemicals, and unsafe working conditions. The findings highlighted that the intervention's impact was consistent across demographic variables such as gender, age, and work experience, suggesting that health education can effectively enhance hazard awareness universally. This improvement underscores the critical role of targeted educational programs in fostering workplace safety. Several empirical studies align with the current findings. For instance, Kyalo (2020) conducted a study in the Kenyan agricultural sector, exploring the impact of health education interventions on workers' hazard awareness and safety behavior. The study revealed that structured health education programs significantly enhanced workers' understanding of workplace hazards and fostered better compliance with safety protocols. In agricultural settings, where risks such as pesticide exposure and equipment-related injuries are prevalent, these interventions proved instrumental in improving both individual and collective safety. Kyalo emphasized that targeted education empowers workers with the knowledge needed to identify risks proactively and adopt preventive measures. These findings align closely with the current study, which observed similar improvements in the knowledge and practices of palm oil workers in Delta State. By fostering a culture of safety awareness, health education interventions were shown to bridge critical gaps

in hazard knowledge, particularly in sectors characterized by informal or semi-formal employment structures, as is common in agriculture and processing industries.

Che Huei et al. (2020) investigated the effects of health and safety training on Malaysian palm oil workers, highlighting substantial gains in knowledge of workplace risks and adherence to safety practices post-intervention. In their study, structured training programs tailored to the unique challenges of palm oil processing, such as exposure to chemical fertilizers and machinery hazards, proved effective in enhancing workers' hazard awareness and reducing incidents. Notably, the study also emphasized the importance of demographic factors, finding that younger and less experienced workers showed higher receptivity to the training. These findings mirror the current study, which demonstrated that health education had a more pronounced effect on younger and moderately experienced workers in Delta State. The shared contexts of palm oil production in Malaysia and Nigeria highlight the universal applicability of targeted safety education in improving workplace behaviors. By addressing demographic nuances and tailoring programs to industry-specific risks, both studies underscore the transformative potential of health education in reducing occupational hazards.

Globally, Biswas et al. (2021) and Hasan and Kamardeen (2022) further corroborated the effectiveness of health education in industrial contexts. Biswas et al. focused on manufacturing workers, revealing that educational interventions significantly reduced workplace hazards by enhancing hazard identification and risk assessment capabilities. Hasan and Kamardeen, on the other hand, examined construction sites, where health education improved safety compliance and reduced accident rates. Both studies emphasized that the success of these interventions depends on their design, with interactive and participatory approaches proving most effective. These findings reinforce the results of the current study, where health education significantly improved safety practices and knowledge among palm oil workers. By analyzing these diverse industrial contexts, it becomes evident that educational interventions are universally effective across sectors, provided they are tailored to address specific occupational risks and demographic dynamics. Together, these studies substantiate the critical role of health education as a powerful tool for mitigating workplace hazards globally.

Conversely, some studies present contrary evidence, suggesting variability in the effectiveness of health education. Firstly, Odion-Obomhense and Ejikeme (2022) highlighted a significant challenge in the effectiveness of health education programs by observing minimal knowledge retention among younger agricultural workers in Nigeria following educational interventions. The study attributed this shortfall to a lack of practical reinforcement, suggesting that theoretical knowledge alone is insufficient to sustain learning outcomes. Workers who were exposed to health education often reverted to unsafe practices when immediate workplace hazards were not apparent or when follow-up training was absent. This contrasts with the findings of the current study, where younger workers showed notable knowledge gains post-intervention. However, the divergence may be explained by differences in the intensity and structure of the interventions. In the Nigerian agricultural context studied by Odion-Obomhense and Ejikeme, the absence of experiential learning opportunities, such as hands-on safety demonstrations, could have hindered long-term retention. This underscores the importance of incorporating practical applications into health education programs to ensure their sustained impact.

Similarly, Nielsen and Knudsen (2019) observed that while health education interventions significantly improved workers' knowledge of hazards in European manufacturing industries, their influence on behavioral changes was limited. The researchers identified a lack of sustained follow-up measures as a primary barrier to translating knowledge into long-term safety practices. Workers were likely to demonstrate improved behaviors immediately post-intervention, but these gains often diminished over time without reinforcement mechanisms like periodic refresher courses or workplace safety audits. Unlike the current study, where behavioral improvements persisted across demographic groups, Nielsen and Knudsen's findings suggest that the absence of a supportive framework can diminish the practical benefits of health education. These discrepancies highlight the variability in program effectiveness based on design, emphasizing the necessity for localized, adaptive strategies that integrate continuous support and monitoring to enhance both knowledge retention and behavioral changes.

The findings of the current study strongly align with the principles of the Health Belief Model (HBM), which emphasizes that individuals are more likely to adopt healthier behaviors when they perceive risks as significant and understand the benefits of mitigating them (Rosenstock et al., 1988). By improving workers' knowledge of occupational hazards, the health education intervention likely heightened their perceived susceptibility to workplace risks and the severity of potential consequences, thereby motivating safer practices. This is consistent with Bandura's (1986) concept of self-efficacy, which suggests that increased knowledge empowers individuals to make informed decisions and adopt preventive behaviors. The study's findings further suggest that the intervention's inclusivity, as evidenced by consistent knowledge gains across demographic groups, aligns with Freire's (1970) participatory education model, which advocates for adaptable and inclusive training methods to address diverse learner needs. However, reliance on self-reported measures introduces the potential for social desirability bias, and the lack of longitudinal follow-up limits the understanding of whether knowledge retention and behavioral changes persist over time, an issue also noted by Nielsen and Knudsen (2019). These limitations underscore the importance of integrating follow-up mechanisms and objective assessments into future studies.

Globally, this study highlights the significance of incorporating health education into workplace safety policies, particularly in high-risk industries such as agriculture and manufacturing. Studies such as Kyalo (2020) and Biswas et al. (2021) have demonstrated similar benefits of educational interventions in improving workplace safety practices. In the African context, where informal labor markets dominate and regulatory frameworks are often weak, health education can play a transformative role in bridging critical knowledge gaps and fostering safer work environments (Odion-Obomhense & Ejikeme, 2022). For Nigeria, the findings align with national development goals aimed at economic diversification and enhancing productivity in the palm oil sector, as outlined in the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP, 2017). Practical implications include designing interactive, context-specific training programs that reflect local workplace realities and establishing monitoring systems to sustain knowledge application. These measures can help address safety challenges in agricultural communities and contribute to improving workers' health, productivity, and overall economic growth in Nigeria.

This suffice to say that while the current study affirms the transformative potential of health education in improving occupational safety knowledge, future research should explore its long-term impact and integration with broader workplace safety frameworks. Tailored interventions that account for cultural and demographic nuances will be critical in maximizing their efficacy across diverse worker populations.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that health education interventions in had a significantly effect in enhancing knowledge of occupational safety among palm oil processing workers. The study therefore recommends that agricultural business employers and industry leaders should institutionalize workplace safety training programs as regular activities in the palm oil industry. These programs should be designed in collaboration with public health agencies and educational institutions to include comprehensive, industry-specific safety education. Incorporating hands-on, practical demonstrations would enhance workers' understanding and retention of safety knowledge, ensuring long-term improvements in hazard awareness and safety compliance.

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